

Computation of the Forward Problem Matrix in Ocean Acoustic Tomography

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ABSTRACT: Measurements of temperature or current by ocean acoustic tomography employ acoustic signals traveling along a path between instruments separated by great distances. The propagation time of a signal is affected by the small changes in temperature or current along the path, so a precise measure of the travel time of the signal is a measure of those properties, averaged over the path taken by the acoustic signal. The computation of the expected acoustic properties using a nominal ocean environment is called “the forward problem”. The computation of ocean properties from the travel times of the acoustic signals is called “the inverse problem”, a core task of ocean acoustic tomography.

The inverse problem usually requires a parameterized ocean model for the sound speed or current variations. Essential preliminary calculations for tomography are path integrals of the ocean model functions over the ray paths traveled by the acoustic signals. These integrations form a matrix that is the “forward problem matrix” for tomography. It specifies precisely the relation of the parameterized ocean model to the recorded acoustic travel times.

The computation of the forward problem matrix can be sensitive in certain situations, such as when acoustic ray paths or forward problem functions are rapidly varying in depth. An approach to such path integrals using Boole’s integration rule is described that has proved to resolve most issues in normal situations. The discussion of these computations also documents two short MATLAB scripts that have been used to implement the computations. The computational steps rely on the acoustic ray tracing code EIGENRAY, or a similar code, that computes a necessary quantity, ray arc length divided by sound speed squared, at fine intervals along the acoustic ray paths.

1. Introduction

Ocean acoustic tomography is a way to observe large-scale oceanic temperature or current processes by the transmission of precisely-designed acoustic signals over distances of 10–5000 km, or more (Munk et al. 1995; Dushaw 2022). The propagation time of those signals is affected by the small changes in temperature or current occurring along the way, so a precise measure of the travel times of the signals is a measure of those properties, averaged over the paths taken by the acoustic signals. In many cases, these paths are well-defined, identifiable acoustic rays that cycle up and down the water column as the rays travel a geodesic path between an acoustic source and an acoustic receiver (e.g., a hydrophone array) (Figure 1). The computation of these properties using a nominal ocean environment is called “the forward problem”. Typically, some 10–20 identifiable acoustic paths are obtained and exploited for acoustic tomography. The computation of properties of the ocean from the travel times of the acoustic signals, i.e., “the inverse problem”, is a core task of ocean acoustic tomography (before using such estimates to better illuminate the nature of the observed oceanographic processes, which is the primary goal). While such computations necessarily employ the sound speed variable, in most cases, sound speed and temperature variations are related by a simple temperature-dependent scaling factor, so estimates of sound speed correspond to estimates of temperature.

The simplest tomography using a single geodesic section usually requires a parameterized ocean model for the sound speed or current changes, consisting of a basis set of two-dimensional functions in range and depth. The combination of these functions and their assumed amplitude statistics is designed to represent the range of possible oceanic variabilities. A tomographic inverse obtains an estimate for the amplitudes of those functions corresponding to an estimate for a sound speed section (ocean model) that is consistent with the ray travel times. An essential, preliminary calculation for the inverse is the integration of the model functions over the ray paths traveled by the acoustic signals. These integrations form a matrix of size (Number of acoustic rays)×(Number of two-dimensional functions), the “forward problem matrix” for tomography. It specifies precisely the relation of the parameterized ocean model to the recorded acoustic travel times.

FIG. 1. A 1000-km long sound speed section from the subtropical Atlantic (Dushaw 2026) and associated acoustic ray paths. From a sound speed profile (left panel), identified acoustic ray paths can be computed (middle panel). Ocean variability is modeled by functions in the vertical, here quasi-geostrophic modes (right panel). The tomography forward problem matrix requires an integration of vertical modes (right panel), combined with horizontal functions, over the acoustic ray paths. The integration often requires special care near the surface, where both ray paths and vertical functions can have rapid variations.

While mostly straightforward integrations, the computations require care to ensure accuracy. Issues mostly arise when rays travel near the sea surface, or when some of the functions rapidly change with depth, such as when functions are needed to represent upper-ocean mixed layers. Although a mostly moot point with modern computational power, attention should be paid to computational expense and memory conservation during the computation as well. This document aims to provide a discussion of an approach to making these computations, while also documenting the provided software to make them.

Since variations in current are two orders of magnitude smaller than variations in sound speed, and the inverse computations for both are identical in form, further discussion of current is omitted. Currents can be measured using reciprocal transmissions (Munk et al. 1995; Dushaw 2026). While this discussion is limited to two-dimensional computations along a single acoustic path, it can be readily adapted to three-dimensional situations (ocean parameterization with

three-dimensional functions) when an array of acoustic paths are employed, e.g., Cornuelle et al. (1989).

2. Theory: Tomography travel times and an ocean model

(Adapted from Dushaw et al. (2026)) A basic equation for tomography represents the acoustic travel time, t_i , along a ray path, s_i , which depends on sound speed as a function of range and depth along the path, $c(r, z)$ (Figure 1), with a small contribution from ocean current, $u(r, z)$, in the direction of the ray paths,

$$t_i = \int_{s_i} \frac{ds}{c(r, z) + u(r, z)}, \quad (1)$$

where ds is an element of ray arc length. The ray path $s_i = s_i(r, z)$ is the i th of a set of rays. As mentioned above, since values for current are small, their contributions are dropped for this discussion. The sound speed can be separated into a contribution from a known reference ocean, $c_0(r, z)$ ($O(1500 \text{ m s}^{-1})$), and a perturbation in sound speed with respect to that reference ocean, $\delta c(r, z)$ ($O(10 \text{ m s}^{-1})$), caused by the oceanographic processes of interest,

$$c(r, z) = c_0(r, z) + \delta c(r, z). \quad (2)$$

A reference sound speed can be derived from the World Ocean Atlas (Dushaw 2026), for example. The perturbation can be caused by any number of oceanographic processes, from internal waves, to mesoscale eddies, to climate change. The inverse problem is to solve for an estimate of the sound speed perturbation and its uncertainty using the acoustic travel times.

Since $\delta c(r, z)/c_0(r, z) \ll 1$, and for small x , $1/(1+x) \approx 1-x$, equation (1), together with (2), can be simplified using a perturbative expansion. With that expansion, the travel time becomes,

$$t_i = t_{0i} - \int_{s_i} \frac{\delta c(r, z)}{c_0^2(r, z)} ds, \quad (3)$$

with the ray's reference travel time computed from the reference ocean,

$$t_{0i} = \int_{s_i} \frac{ds}{c_0(r, z)}. \quad (4)$$

In these equations, a fixed ray approximation is assumed, that is, the sound speed perturbations are assumed not to significantly disturb the ray path geometry. Often the inverse involves an iteration or two to obtain a self-consistent result: compute an initial correction to the reference sound speed by adding the first estimate for the perturbation, then repeat the inverse using the corrected reference sound speed with its associated corrected ray paths.

The sound speed field, $\delta c(r, z)$, is modeled as a superposition of a set of functions in range and depth, together with their statistical properties, designed to represent ocean variability, termed “the ocean model”. The statistical properties are things like the variances of function amplitudes, or the wavenumber spectrum for variability horizontally, usually assumed to be red, with longer wavelengths having greater variance. A common model is,

$$\delta c(r, z) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_V} V_i(z) \left[A_{i0}^0 + \sum_{j=1}^{N_H} (A_{ij}^1 \cos(K_j r) + A_{ij}^2 \sin(K_j r)) \right], \quad (5)$$

where the $V_i(z)$ are a suitable set of vertical functions (e.g., Figure 1, right panel), the horizontal variability is modeled as a truncated Fourier series with wavenumbers K_j (Cornuelle et al. 1989; Dushaw and Sagen 2016). Combining vertical and horizontal indexes into a single index, the A_{ij} 's into a single vector of amplitudes, \mathbf{m} , and the combinations of vertical functions and sinusoids into a single set of functions, $P_k(r, z)$, the sound speed perturbation becomes,

$$\delta c(r, z) = \sum_{k=1}^N m_k P_k(r, z). \quad (6)$$

There are N_V vertical functions and N_H wavenumbers, which combine to form $N = N_V(1 + 2N_H)$ total number of functions $P_k(r, z)$. Typical numbers employed are 5 vertical functions and 10 wavenumbers, corresponding to an ocean model of 105 functions. Generally speaking, the functions $P_k(r, z)$ can take any form required, or convenient, for the oceanographic problem at hand. For example, Dushaw et al. (2026) employed the two-dimensional EOFs of an appropriate covariance derived from an global ocean state estimate. The forward problem matrix, denoted as the operator \mathbf{G} , is calculated by substituting the assumed parameterized ocean model in equation 3 above giving,

$$G_{ik} = - \int_{s_i} \frac{P_k(r, z)}{c_0^2(r, z)} ds. \quad (7)$$

Combining equations 3, 6, and 7 gives,

$$\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{G}*\mathbf{m} + \epsilon, \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{d} = \{t_i - t_{0i}\}$ is a vector of the observed ray travel times relative to the reference travel times, \mathbf{m} is the vector of model parameters to solve for, and ϵ is data noise. If there are J travel time data and K model functions, then \mathbf{G} is dimension $J \times K$.

The discussion above is a specific example of how measurements generally can be used to compute objective maps of ocean variability. To compute an objective map using oceanographic data with any set of ocean model functions, a required step is to compute samples of those functions in the same way that the measurement technique measured the ocean. If one had an array of thermistor moorings with instruments at a set of locations $\{r_i, z_i\}$, for example, the equivalent to equation (1) would be

$$T_i = \int \delta(r_i, z_i) T(r, z) drdz \quad (9)$$

where $T(r, z)$ is the temperature section and $\delta(r, z)$ is the delta function. The delta function is used to represent the point measurements of thermistors, in contrast to the path integrals of tomography (Dushaw and Sagen 2016). The forward problem matrix in this case, the equivalent of equation (7) but for point measurements, is simply,

$$G_{ik} = \int \delta(r_i, z_i) P_k(r, z) drdz = P_k(r_i, z_i). \quad (10)$$

The inverse is applied to the data, $\{T_i\}$.

3. The inverse

The inverse problem itself is not directly relevant to computing the “forward problem matrix”. This section is included to put that quantity in its inverse-problem context. The inverse of tomographic data to determine the amplitudes of the P_k functions, hence $\delta c(r, z)$, often employs the “stochastic inverse” (Aki and Richards 1980). This method is equivalent to fitting the ocean

model to the data using weighted least squares. The inverse itself involves a short sequence of matrix computations. The notation of Tarantola (2005) is followed.

Define the model parameter covariance, \mathbf{R}_{mm} , and the data noise covariance, $\mathbf{R}_{\epsilon\epsilon}$, both assumed to be diagonal, so that the data covariance is,

$$\mathbf{R}_{dd} = \mathbf{G} * \mathbf{R}_{mm} * \mathbf{G}^T + \mathbf{R}_{\epsilon\epsilon}. \quad (11)$$

One equation for the inverse operator is

$$\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{R}_{mm} * \mathbf{G}^T / \mathbf{R}_{dd}. \quad (12)$$

The solution for the estimated model parameters, $\hat{\mathbf{m}}$, is then

$$\hat{\mathbf{m}} = \mathbf{L} * \mathbf{d}. \quad (13)$$

The estimated model parameter error covariance is

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{R}_{mm} - \mathbf{L} * \mathbf{G} * \mathbf{R}_{mm}, \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{L} * \mathbf{G}$ is the resolution matrix, with $\hat{\mathbf{m}} = \mathbf{R} * \mathbf{m}$. \mathbf{R}_{mm} is the “prior” error covariance, referring to the ocean model unconstrained by any data. Maps or averages of the solution in sound speed and their uncertainties can be readily computed from the estimated $\hat{\mathbf{m}}$ and its uncertainty.

Once the $\hat{\mathbf{m}}$ model amplitudes have been estimated, it is a simple matter to compute the estimated sound speed correction from equation (6). The estimate for $\delta c(r, z)$ can then be added to the reference sound speed, $c_0(r, z)$, to form the estimate of the corrected sound speed field. Ideally, computing the acoustic forward problem again using the corrected environment produces travel times that match those observed, within uncertainty. (If there remains a mismatch, usually from a degree of non-linearity, further measures can be taken, e.g., an iteration.)

4. Ray tracing: Sound speed and raypaths

Standard ray tracing is used to compute the expected ray travel times, angles, and paths along the sound speed section (Jensen et al. 2011). The ray code EIGENRAY (Dushaw and Colosi 1998; Dushaw 2024), designed specifically for tomography, saves the paths of user-selected eigenrays (rays that travel from a specific acoustic source to a specific acoustic receiver), together with the values for $ds/c_0^2(r, z)$ along those paths (Equation (7); Figure 2; Table), which are needed to compute the integrals for the forward problem matrix.

FIG. 2. A schematic figure showing the relation of increments of ray path, $s(r, z)$ (see the Table), to the sound speed profile or model vertical function. The ray path is computed at small range increments h_i (e.g., 5–200 m), but saved at a larger, user-specified increment (e.g., 1000 m). The value of ds/c^2 associated with the saved path increment is required to calculate the “forward problem” matrix used in the inversion of travel times. It may be more precise, though perhaps excessively so, as well as laborious, to calculate the matrix while simultaneously computing the ray trace. Equivalent precision could perhaps be obtained by saving the computed path at smaller range increments. (From Dushaw and Colosi (1998).)

Table: Some Ray Path Data

r (m)	z (m)	ds/c ² (r, z)
0.0000	-1000.0000	0.000457316
1000.0000	-1202.8949	0.000457518
2000.0000	-1406.7037	0.000456618
3000.0000	-1607.2372	0.000455186
4000.0000	-1802.3092	0.000453593
5000.0000	-1991.1033	0.000451810
6000.0000	-2172.5937	0.000449909
7000.0000	-2345.9371	0.000447962
8000.0000	-2510.4942	0.000446015
9000.0000	-2665.7484	0.000444109
10000.0000	-2811.2833	0.000442310
11000.0000	-2946.9977	0.000440613
12000.0000	-3072.7323	0.000439045
13000.0000	-3188.4542	0.000437605
14000.0000	-3294.1450	0.000436285
15000.0000	-3389.6918	0.000435094
16000.0000	-3475.0457	0.000434026
17000.0000	-3550.0747	0.000433086
18000.0000	-3614.6480	0.000432285
19000.0000	-3668.7098	0.000431625
20000.0000	-3712.2203	0.000431108
21000.0000	-3745.1286	0.000430734
22000.0000	-3767.3858	0.000430507
23000.0000	-3778.9538	0.000430428
24000.0000	-3779.8114	0.000430497
25000.0000	-3769.9577	0.000430714
26000.0000	-3749.4116	0.000431077
27000.0000	-3718.2098	0.000431585
28000.0000	-3676.4009	0.000432234
29000.0000	-3624.0362	0.000433025
30000.0000	-3561.1584	0.000433954
31000.0000	-3487.8157	0.000435013
32000.0000	-3404.1255	0.000436195
33000.0000	-3310.2270	0.000437504
34000.0000	-3206.1833	0.000438934
35000.0000	-3092.0840	0.000440490
36000.0000	-2967.9771	0.000442176
37000.0000	-2833.8686	0.000443966
38000.0000	-2689.9075	0.000445865
39000.0000	-2536.1916	0.000447810
40000.0000	-2373.0844	0.000449752
41000.0000	-2201.1106	0.000451651
42000.0000	-2020.8840	0.000453431
43000.0000	-1833.2511	0.000455018
44000.0000	-1639.2490	0.000456459
45000.0000	-1439.6386	0.000457425
46000.0000	-1236.2774	0.000457405
47000.0000	-1032.8370	0.000454830

...

Figure 2 shows a schematic figure of the ray trace along a small section of a ray path. The ray trace code marches horizontally at small range increments of $O(5\text{--}200\text{ m})$, denoted h_i . These small range increments vary in size along the ray path - shorter lengths are required near the surface, longer lengths deeper, since the scales of sound speed variability vary with depth. The ray paths do not need to be saved at those short increments, however, so the paths are saved at a larger, user-specified increment, e.g., 1000 m as in the Table. However, the values of $ds/c_0^2(r, z)$ along the path need to be computed over small increments, since sound speed is varying along the path. In a ray integration step, at position (r_i, z_i) , this quantity is,

$$\frac{ds}{c_0^2(r_i, z_i)} \approx \frac{\sqrt{(\delta r)^2 + (\delta z)^2}}{c_0^2(r_i, z_i)}, \quad (15)$$

where $\delta r = h_i = r_{i+1} - r_i$ and $\delta z = z_{i+1} - z_i$. Or, equivalently, since $\tan\theta_i = \delta z/h_i$, where θ_i is the ray angle,

$$\frac{ds}{c_0^2(r_i, z_i)} \approx \frac{h_i}{c_0^2(r_i, z_i)\cos\theta_i}. \quad (16)$$

This latter form is convenient since the variable $\cos\theta$ is available as an inherent variable of the ray tracing. (Computationally, it also saves a square root and two squares.)

Between saved points along the ray path, the values of $ds_i/c_0^2(r_i, z_i)$ from each integrating step h_i are summed to obtain the value for the user-specified increments. Thus, the value for $ds_j/c_0^2(r_j, z_j)$ saved by the ray trace program for the j -th user-specified increment, e.g., the third column of the Table, is

$$\frac{ds_j}{c_0^2(r_j, z_j)} = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{h_i}{c_0^2(r_i, z_i)\cos\theta_i}. \quad (17)$$

The sum of the h_i equals the user-specified increment (1000 m in the Table).

5. Integration of forward problem matrix

The elements of the forward problem matrix precisely quantify the effect of the ocean model functions on the ray travel times. The path integral of equation (7) that defines those elements is the theoretical representation of that sensitivity. However, for the particular geometries of some model functions and/or ray paths, numerically computing the path integrals accurately and robustly can be challenging. Problems have arisen in computing such integrals when rays turn near the bottom of a function representing a thin, sharp, surface-mixed layer, for example.

In this case, the coarseness of the saved ray path can misrepresent the precise ray sampling of the function. One solution to this issue could be to increase the resolution of the saved ray increments. Such a strategy would be computationally expensive, and it is not guaranteed to resolve the issue.

From an examination of equations (5)–(7), it is apparent that the integration problem is separable into a function of depth times a function of range. That is, each $P_k(r, z)$ is a product with a form like

$$P_k(r, z) = V_i(z) \cos(K_j r), \quad (18)$$

where the index k is a combination of the i, j indices. To compute the path integral then, one can separately interpolate the vertical and horizontal functions along the paths, before combining them to compute the path integration. While it is not always the case, the separation in depth and range functions is common in many inverse computations. Dushaw et al. (2026) provides a different example, where two-dimensional Empirical Orthogonal Functions (EOFs) were used. Nevertheless, the computation here with separation of variables illustrates the basic considerations.

Horizontally, the sinusoidal functions are simple, large-scale, and smoothly varying, so that a simple interpolation is adequate. In the associated code “forward2C.m”, the ranges and depths of a ray path are given by the variables rr and zz . The interpolation range values should be the mid-point of a user-specified interval. Interpolation of the horizontal variability is simply,

$$HH(rr, j) = \text{interp1}(R, \cos(K_j * R), rr), \quad (19)$$

if the horizontal function is $\cos(K_j * R)$, with wavenumber K_j at range values R . In this MATLAB code, the horizontal function is interpolated one-dimensionally by the MATLAB function “interp1” to its values at ray-range values, rr .

In the example software, the model horizontal and vertical functions are organized in the separate MATLAB program “for2Dmodel.m”, while the ray integrations are by the calling function “forward2C.m”. A modular organization of the software for these computations is more convenient and less error prone.

Vertically, one could similarly compute a one-dimensional interpolation

$$MM(zz,i) = interp1(ZM, M_i(ZM), zz), \quad (20)$$

with vertical functions $M_i(ZM)(= V_i(z))$ (using the notation of the example software). The ray path values of zz cycle up and down the water column, but the one-dimensional interpolation is well-defined. We seek accurate values for the vertical functions along the ray paths specified at the user-specified range increments. Such an interpolation roughly computes those, but, as mentioned above, it has sometimes proved inaccurate.

Instead, a weighted average of the $M_i(z)$ are computed over the user-specified range increments, and these values are used as the value of the function for that increment. The value of a vertical function associated with each ray path increment is computed using Boole's rule (Abramowitz and Stegun 1965) (Section 25.4.14, page 886)¹. While formally a procedure for computing integration, using it to compute a weighted average has appeared to resolve some of the sensitivity experienced with the cruder interpolations.

Using Boole's rule, the vertical function is first interpolated on 5 equally-spaced depths over an increment, beginning and ending with values of the user-specified increments.

```
for k = 1 : Nvert
    FF2 = M(:, k);
    for iqq = 0 : 4,
        mm(:, iqq + 1) = interp1(ZM, FF2, zz + dzz * iqq); % The (f0, f1, ... f4) of Boole's rule
    end
...

```

(21)

¹This integration algorithm is sometimes erroneously referred to as “Bode’s rule” because of a typographical error that appeared in the Abramowitz and Stegun reference. “Boole” refers to English mathematician George Boole (1815–1864), he of “Boolean algebra”. See: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boole's_rule.

where d_{zz} is 1/4 the depth change of the ray path over the user-specified increment. Those 5 values are then summed by Boole's rule to form an average,

$$MM(:,k) = \frac{2 * 0.25}{45} * (7 * mm(:,1) + 32 * mm(:,2) + 12 * mm(:,3) + 32 * mm(:,4) + 7 * mm(:,5));$$

...

(22)

The result is a more accurate, robust computation of the value of the vertical functions associated with each ray path increment.

If ww is the vector of values of $ds_i/c_0^2(r_i, z_i)$ along a ray path (third column of the Table), then the MM can be weighted by it

$$MM(:,k) = MM(:,k) .* ww; \quad \% \text{ A Hadamard product}$$

(23)

end

With MM and HH computed this way, the path integral (7) is just the vector product,

$$G(nray, ncount) = -MM(:,nv)' * HH(:,nh); \quad (24)$$

for vertical function nv , horizontal function nh , and the two-dimensional function that is a combination of those, index $ncount$. The resulting matrix is the forward problem matrix, the \mathbf{G} of equation (8).

One primary advantage of this separation-of-variables approach is its computational efficiency in that two-dimensional functions do not have to be stored and interpolated. If the two-dimensional functions are specifically required and inseparable, then other appropriate computations would of course be required, as in Dushaw et al. (2026).

6. Discussion

This document reviews the basic equations for ocean acoustic tomography in the open ocean, highlighting the central role of the “forward problem matrix”, denoted \mathbf{G} . Its aim is to emphasize that the computation of this matrix is occasionally sensitive to ray path or function idiosyncrasies, hence the path integrals of that computation should be done cautiously. A computational approach using Boole's rule has proved successful. The discussion simultaneously documents two associated programs of MATLAB software used for those computations, “for2Dmodel.m” and “forward2C.m”.

The integrals described here necessarily require approximations to numerically compute them. In the experience of the author, any errors resulting from the approximations are negligible, that is, of negligible concern to the ultimate oceanographic estimates. Ultimately, the goal of an inverse is to produce *by any means* an ocean environment that is consistent with the recorded data. The inverse computations using the path integrations described here have been shown to do that. On occasion iterations are required to refine the solution, which is, however, a consequence of a violation of the fixed-ray approximation. Such a situation indicates the inverse problem is slightly non-linear, rather than an error in computing the forward problem matrix.

However, every inverse problem is unique, and it is important to pay attention to the nature of the integrals to detect and correct for pathologies that may arise. While a reader may find themselves with situations are not exactly consistent with the computational approach described here, it is hoped that at least the general concerns and strategy for accurate computation discussed may prove valuable.

References

- Abramowitz, M., and I. A. Stegun, 1965: *Handbook of Mathematical Functions with Formulas, Graphs, and Mathematical Tables*, Applied Mathematics Series, Vol. 55. Ninth Dover printing, tenth GPO printing ed., Dover Publications, New York, URL <http://numerical.recipes/aands/>.
- Aki, K., and P. G. Richards, 1980: *Quantitative Seismology: Theory and Methods*. Vol. 2., W. H. Freeman, 932 pp.
- Cornuelle, B. D., W. Munk, and P. Worcester, 1989: Ocean acoustic tomography from ships. *J. Geophys. Res., Oceans*, **94**, 6232–5250, <https://doi.org/10.1029/JC094iC05p06232>.
- Dushaw, B. D., 2022: Surprises in physical oceanography: Contributions from ocean acoustic tomography. *Tellus A: Dynamic Meteorology and Oceanography*, **74**, 33–67, <https://doi.org/10.16993/tellusa.39>.
- Dushaw, B. D., 2024: EIGENRAY: FORTRAN computer code for computing long-range, deep-ocean acoustic propagation by ray tracing. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10816780>.
- Dushaw, B. D., 2026: On measurement of temperature and current in the Atlantic near 26°N by ocean acoustic tomography (submitted). *J. Atmos. Oceanic Technol.*, **XX**, XXX–XXX, <https://doi.org/10.1175/JTECH-D-26-0009>.
- Dushaw, B. D., and J. A. Colosi, 1998: Ray tracing for ocean acoustic tomography. *Applied Physics Laboratory, University of Washington*, **APL-UW TM 3-98**.
- Dushaw, B. D., D. Menemenlis, and J. A. Colosi, 2026: Ocean observing system design: Transatlantic acoustic propagation for acoustic thermometry. *J. Atmos. Oceanic Technol.*, **43**, 267–287, <https://doi.org/10.1175/JTECH-D-24-0124.1>.
- Dushaw, B. D., and H. Sagen, 2016: A comparative study of the properties of moored/point and acoustic tomography/integral observations of Fram Strait using objective mapping techniques. *J. Atmos. Oceanic Technol.*, **33**, 2079–2093, <https://doi.org/10.1175/JTECH-D-15-0251.1>.
- Jensen, F. B., W. A. Kuperman, M. B. Porter, and H. Schmidt, 2011: *Computational Ocean Acoustics*. Springer-Verlag, 794 pp., <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-8678-8>.
- Munk, W. H., P. F. Worcester, and C. Wunsch, 1995: *Ocean Acoustic Tomography*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, England, 433 pp. pp.
- Tarantola, A., 2005: *Inverse Problem Theory and Methods for Parameter Estimation*. Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics, Philadelphia, 342 pp.